

ORTHOTROPIC ELASTIC-PLASTIC BEHAVIOR OF AS4/APC-2 THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE AT ELEVATED TEMPERATURES

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ABSTRACT

Inelastic and strength properties of AS4/APC-2 composites were characterized with respect to temperature variation by using a one parameter orthotropic plasticity model and a one parameter failure criterion. Simple uniaxial off-axis tension tests were performed on coupon specimens of unidirectional AS4/APC-2 thermoplastic composite at various temperatures. To avoid the complication caused by the extension-shear coupling effect in off-axis testing, new tabs were designed and used on the test specimens. The experimental results showed that the nonlinear behavior of constitutive relations and the strength can be characterized quite well using the one parameter plasticity model and the failure criterion, respectively.

INTRODUCTION

AS4/APC-2 is a high-performance thermoplastic composite material based on polyether-ether-ketone (PEEK) reinforced with AS4 graphite fiber. Compared with epoxy-based composite materials, AS4/APC-2 has improved impact toughness and damage tolerance as well as good creep and fatigue resistance. It also has good environmental properties, such as high temperature performance (T_g : 290°F), low water absorption and excellent solvent and fire resistance.

The increase in toughness and resistance of AS4/APC-2 is from the increased ductility of APC-2 PEEK resin. The greater ductility of the matrix implies more pronounced plasticity in the matrix-dominant deformation. Thus, characterizing the nonlinear stress-strain relations may be needed in the design and application of thermoplastic composite structures.

Recently, a one parameter orthotropic plasticity model was proposed by Sun and Chen for fiber composites [1]. The parameter was obtained from the simple uniaxial tension tests of off-axis specimens. They concluded that a one parameter plasticity model is most suitable for describing the nonlinear behavior of composites exhibiting little plasticity in the fiber direction. This model is very attractive for characterizing the inelastic properties of continuous fiber reinforced composites at elevated temperature environments because of the simplicity offered by the off-axis tension test.

In the present study the elastic-plastic properties of the AS4/APC-2 composite with respect to temperature variation are characterized using the one parameter plasticity model. A one-parameter failure criterion is also presented and evaluated with experimental results.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The 0°, 15°, 30°, 45°, and 90° coupon specimens were cut from the [0₁₀] panels; the thickness was 1.27 ± 0.025 mm (0.05 ± 0.001 inch). The specimen length was 254.0 mm (10.0 inch) and the width was 19.0 ± 0.25 mm (0.75 ± 0.01 inch).

Rigid glass/epoxy tabs were used in testing 0° and 90° coupon specimens where extension shear coupling is absent; newly designed shear deformable flexible tabs were used in testing 15°, 30° and 45° coupon specimens where extension shear coupling exists. The shear deformable end tab was developed by Sun and Berreth [2] using silicon rubber reinforced with bi-directional E-glass knit. They demonstrated that the use of this tab could produce an almost uniform stress field in off-axis coupon

specimens with conventional hydraulic grips. In the present experiments, two kinds of flexible matrix systems were used together with fiberglass knit for the new shear deformable tabs. The silicon rubber matrix tab used in [2] was too weak to transmit enough load at elevated temperatures. The flexible epoxy system (Flex Epoxy 103, Thermoset Plastic Inc.) whose flexibility can be tailored by choosing the ratio of resin and hardener, was used as the matrix of the tab. This tab was used for tests at room temperature and 150°F. The FM1000 adhesive film (thickness : 0.25 mm [0.01 inch], American Cyanamid Co.) was used to fabricate the second kind of tab used for tests at 250°F and 350°F.

All tests were performed at a constant strain rate control of 300 $\mu\epsilon$ /min. Longitudinal and transverse strains were measured by strain gages (Micro Measurement EA-13-125AC-350) mounted at the center of the specimen. The measured analog signals were converted into digital signals. The signals were stored and analyzed by a micro-computer data system.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Stress-strain curves for 0°, 15°, 30°, 45°, 90° coupon specimens tested at 75°F, 150°F, 250°F, and 350°F were obtained. Figures 1 and 2 present the stress-strain curves for all off-axis specimens at 75°F and 250°F, respectively.

Fig. 1. Stress-strain curves for off-axis specimens at 75°F.

Fig. 2. Stress-strain curves for off-axis specimens at 250°F.

It is noted that the longitudinal modulus does not change with respect to temperature variation, but the apparent moduli of other off-axis specimens drop to 80-85% of the modulus of room temperature at 250°F, and to 45-60% at 350°F. The decreasing rate of the apparent moduli of off-axis specimens becomes higher over 250°F. It is evident that the longitudinal modulus remained unchanged since it is dominated by the graphite fiber which is not sensitive to temperature variation. Since the transverse property is dominated by the APC-2 matrix, which is sensitive to temperature variation, the shear and the transverse moduli decrease significantly as temperature increases, especially at temperatures near the glass transition temperature (290°F).

The longitudinal strength does not change with temperature variation as expected. The apparent strengths of off-axis specimens drop to 40-48% of the room temperature strength at 350°F. However, the rate of reduction in the apparent strengths of off-axis specimens does not seem sensitive to temperature near the glass transition temperature of the PEEK resin.

ONE PARAMETER PLASTICITY MODEL

In this study, a one-parameter plastic potential of the form

$$2f = \sigma_{22}^2 + 2a_{66}\sigma_{12}^2 \quad (1)$$

is used which was proposed by Sun and Chen [1]. From this plastic potential, the plastic strain increments are derived:

$$d\varepsilon_{ij}^p = d\lambda \frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma_{ij}} \quad \text{or} \quad \begin{Bmatrix} d\varepsilon_{11}^p \\ d\varepsilon_{22}^p \\ d\gamma_{12}^p \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ \sigma_{22} \\ 2a_{66}\sigma_{12} \end{Bmatrix} d\lambda \quad (2)$$

where γ_{12} is an engineering shear strain. The corresponding effective stress and effective plastic strain increments are defined by

$$\bar{\sigma} = \sqrt{3f} \quad (3)$$

and

$$d\bar{\varepsilon}^p = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} \left[(d\varepsilon_{22}^p)^2 + \frac{1}{2a_{66}} (d\gamma_{12}^p)^2 \right]^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

respectively. The complete orthotropic plastic flow rule is defined if the parameters a_{66} and $d\lambda$ are determined.

1. Off-Axis Tension Test

To determine $d\lambda$, the effective stress-effective plastic strain relation must be established. This can be accomplished from the result of tension tests on off-axis specimens.

Let x-axis be the uniaxial loading direction which makes an angle θ with the fiber direction x_1 -axis. The stresses referring to the material principal axes (x_1 and x_2) are related to the applied uniaxial stress σ_x as

$$\sigma_{11} = \cos^2\theta \sigma_x, \quad \sigma_{22} = \sin^2\theta \sigma_x, \quad \sigma_{12} = -\sin\theta\cos\theta \sigma_x \quad (5)$$

Substitution of equations (5) into (3) and (4) yields

$$\bar{\sigma} = h(\theta) \sigma_x \quad (6)$$

where

$$h(\theta) = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2}} \left[\sin^4 \theta + 2a_{66} \sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (7)$$

Using a similar coordinate transformation for strains and the definition for $d\bar{\epsilon}^P$ as given by equation (4), we obtain

$$d\bar{\epsilon}^P = d\epsilon_x^P / h(\theta) \quad \text{or} \quad \bar{\epsilon}^P = \epsilon_x^P / h(\theta) \quad (8)$$

Thus, the desired relation between $\bar{\sigma}$ and $\bar{\epsilon}^P$ can now be obtained from the experimentally obtained relation between σ_x and ϵ_x^P . It follows that

$$\frac{d\bar{\sigma}}{d\bar{\epsilon}^P} = h^2(\theta) \frac{d\sigma_x}{d\epsilon_x^P} \quad (9)$$

and

$$d\lambda = \frac{3}{2} \frac{1}{h^2(\theta)} \frac{d\epsilon_x^P}{d\sigma_x} \frac{d\sigma_x}{\sigma_x} \quad (10)$$

Since the $\bar{\sigma}$ - $\bar{\epsilon}^P$ relation should be unique in monotonic loading for the given material, the parameter a_{66} must be chosen so that the resulting $\bar{\sigma}$ - $\bar{\epsilon}^P$ relation is independent of θ .

The procedure for determining the one-parameter plasticity model becomes very simple. In theory, only two off-axis specimens with different θ 's are required to determine a_{66} . Note that for $\theta = 90^\circ$, $h(\theta) = \sqrt{3}/2$ and, thus, the stress-strain relation for the 90° -specimen is not affected by the choice of a_{66} and can be conveniently used to construct the master effective stress-effective plastic strain curve for the composite.

Experimental results indicate that for fiber composites there is no well defined yield point. In view of this, the master effective stress-effective plastic strain curve can be fitted as a power law,

$$\bar{\epsilon}^P = A(\bar{\sigma})^n \quad (\bar{\sigma} \text{ in MPa}) \quad (11)$$

which implies that yielding occurs from the start of loading.

2. Parameter Evaluation

From the off-axis stress-strain curves as shown in Figs. 1-2, the relation between σ_x and ϵ_x^P can be established. These relations for all the off-axis angles considered collapsed into one master curve with $a_{66} = 1.5$ when plotted in terms of effective stress and effective plastic strain, see Fig. 3. Moreover, the value $a_{66} = 1.5$ seems valid for temperatures up to 350°F , indicating that the plastic orthotropy of AS4/APC-2 is independent of temperature.

Fig. 3. Effective stress-effective plastic strain curves for off-axis specimens with $a_{66} = 1.5$ at 250°F .

By taking the logarithm for the power law, equation (11), and using linear curve fitting, the coefficients A and n can be determined. The results indicate that n = 7.0 is adequate for temperatures up to 250°F, and that coefficient A is related to temperature as

$$\ln(A) = 0.023T - 42.07 \quad (12)$$

for temperatures below the glass transition point.

The stress-strain curve in loading can be predicted using the following equation.

$$\epsilon_x = \frac{\sigma_x}{E_x} + \epsilon_x^p = \frac{\sigma_x}{E_x} + [h(\theta)]^{n+1} A \sigma_x^n \quad (13)$$

Figure 4 shows the total stress-strain curves, experimental and predicted, for the off-axis specimens at 250°F. Agreement between data and prediction is excellent.

Fig. 4. Measured and predicted longitudinal stress-strain curves at 250°F.

3. Plastic Poisson's Ratio

The validity of a_{66} can be checked by the comparison of the plastic Poisson's ratios obtained from theory and experiment. The plastic Poisson's ratio is defined as

$$\nu_{66}^p = - \frac{d\epsilon_y^p}{d\epsilon_x^p} \quad (14)$$

From equations (2) and (5) and the transformation law on strain components, the plastic strain increments in x-direction and y-direction can be obtained, which in turn leads to

$$\nu_{66}^p = \frac{(2a_{66}-1)\cos^2\theta}{\sin^2\theta+2a_{66}\cos^2\theta} \quad (15)$$

In the off-axis tension test, longitudinal and transverse strains were measured, from which the plastic strains can be obtained and, thus, the plastic Poisson's ratio.

Figure 5 shows that the predicted plastic Poisson's ratio with $a_{66} = 1.5$, and the experimental data match well up to 250°F except for the data from the 30° off-axis specimen tested at 250°F.

Fig. 5. Measured and predicted plastic Poisson's ratios.

ONE PARAMETER FAILURE CRITERION

We propose a dual mode failure criterion for the AS4/APC-2 composite. For fiber breakage, the failure criterion is assumed to be

$$\sigma_{11} \geq X \quad (16)$$

where X is the longitudinal strength. For matrix-dominated failure, the criterion is given by

$$\sigma_{22}^2 + 2a_{66}^* \sigma_{12}^2 = k_{cr}^2 \quad (17)$$

where k_{cr} is a critical value and a_{66}^* a strength orthotropy parameter to be determined.

Parameters a_{66}^* value k_{cr} were examined for temperature variation. It was found that the a_{66}^* is not sensitive to temperature variation (below T.G.), but k_{cr} decreases as temperature increases.

For the AS4/APC-2 composite, it was found that

$$a_{66}^* = 0.74 \quad (18)$$

$$k_{cr}^2 = -27.2T + 11124 \quad (19)$$

for temperatures below the glass transition temperature. Note that in the above equation k_{cr} is in MPa and T is in °F.

The experimental data and the predicted strengths in room temperature from the one parameter criterion and Tsai-Hill criterion are compared in Fig 6. The two criteria agree except for small off-axis angles where the one-parameter criterion seems more accurate than the Tsai-Hill criterion.

CONCLUSION

Elastic-plastic behavior of AS4/APC-2 thermoplastic composite can be well characterized by using the one-parameter orthotropic plasticity model. The orthotropic plasticity parameter a_{66} and the power index n are not affected by temperature variation; the logarithm of coefficient A varies linearly with temperature up to the glass transition temperature.

The failure strength of off-axis specimens can be predicted by using the one parameter failure criterion. Temperature effects on the strength of off-axis specimens can be described with the temperature-independent strength orthotropy parameter a_{66}^* and the critical potential value k_{cr}^2 , which has a linear relationship with temperature variation. For specimens with small off-axis angles the one parameter failure criterion is more accurate than the Tsai-Hill failure criterion.

Fig. 6. Measured and predicted apparent strengths for off-axis specimens at 75°F.

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